

A NOVEL TEST LOAD FRAME FOR CHARACTERIZING THE BUCKLING RESISTANCE OF THICK SANDWICH PANELS

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Abstract

The latest design standards and guidelines for wind turbine rotor blades encourage model validation through sub-component testing, offering the incentive of lower material reduction factors. Structural stability, i.e., the buckling resistance, stands out among the critical design parameters. This aspect is crucial for the large, aerodynamic shell-like areas constructed from lightweight sandwich materials. In support of this model validation, our research introduces a novel test load frame designed to assess the stability of composite sandwich plates under quasi-static compressive loads. The load frame accommodates relatively thick plates with adjustable aspect ratios and aims to: (i) provide simply supported boundaries on all four edges, (ii) enable rapid installation of the specimen while accurately aligning the plate to the load axis, and (iii) allow for easy mounting in a standard universal testing machine. We successfully conducted a proof-of-concept test. For this purpose, a sandwich configuration consisting of glass, epoxy, and balsa wood was manufactured. It was tested quasi-statically to failure, while strains and out-of-plane deflections were monitored using a digital image correlation system. The critical buckling load was predicted using both an analytical orthotropic plate model and a finite element model, with the theoretical results overestimating the experimental values by 1.3% to 5.7%.

1. Introduction

Wind turbine blades are typically constructed from thin-walled cylindrical and airfoil-shaped shells, primarily composed of fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs). These shells, susceptible to buckling [[1]-[2]], are designed with sandwich panels for enhanced stability, incorporating thin FRP skins and core materials like balsa wood, polyvinyl chloride (PVC), or polyurethane (PU) foam for lightweight purposes. Resin-filled grooves and holes in the core material aid resin infusion during manufacturing and accommodate the curvature of the shells. In [3], the importance of realistically representing core materials, considering resin uptake in sandwich constructions for wind turbine blades, was emphasized. Reducing resin uptake offers notable benefits to the specific flexural strength of the core [4]. However, the challenge lies in the complex experimental validation required to assess the impact of resin uptake on buckling resistance, particularly in adherence to the new design standard for blade structures [5][6]. This advocates for experimental validation to minimize partial material safety factors during the design process.

In response to this need, our research introduces a novel load frame designed for characterizing the buckling resistance of thick sandwich constructions [7]. This unique test frame accommodates simply supported flat plates with variable aspect ratios. The load frame can be mounted in standard universal testing machines. Moreover, we describe the proof of concept test and validate numerical and analytical predictions of the critical buckling resistance with the experimental results.

2. Methods

2.1 Experiment

2.1.1 Load frame design

The sandwich plate width and thickness can be adjusted at the lateral, as well as at the upper and lower boundaries, to accommodate variable plate dimensions. The frame can host spanning dimensions of 1.2m in height, 0.3m to 1.2m in width, and up to 0.05m in thickness. Its segmented, articulated roller bearing supports allow the plate edges to twist non-uniformly out of the plane at the load application and load reception positions. The tested plate is simply supported, with modular roller bearings for the horizontal edges and 'knife edges' for the vertical boundaries. The frame is optimized for compatibility with standard universal uniaxial testing machines, having clamping heads with flat bearing surfaces.

Figure 1. Load frame design: a. overview, b. front view (side B), and c. side view.

2.1.2 Manufacture of specimen

A sandwich panel of 1.2 m in width and 1.2 m in height was manufactured with Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion Molding (VARIM) using E-glass fabrics of type SAERTEX X-E-778g/m² infused with epoxy resin of type Westlake EPIKOTE™ Resin MGS® RIMR035c with EPIKURE™ Agent MGS® RIMH037 for the skins and a balsa wood core of type BALTEK SB.100 with a nominal density of 148kg/m³. The total thickness of the sandwich was measured to be 27.82 ± 0.42 mm around the plate edges (**Figure 2a**). Additionally, the average thickness of the balsa wood, measured along the plate edges, was 24.86 mm, resulting in an average thickness of 0.74 mm per $[\pm 45_2]$ ply.

The layup was built symmetrically, i.e., $[\pm 45_2/\text{Balsa}/\pm 45_2]$, with the last two biaxial plies rotated by 90° in the roll direction. During the infusion, a table was heated to 40°C. After the infusion, the sandwich was cured for 12 hours at 40°C.

About 25 mm balsa wood was removed from the load-introducing plate edges (**Figure 2b**) and replaced with short-glass-fiber-filled epoxy adhesive to enhance a smoother load transition in the sandwich structure, reducing the risk of local core crushing due to the low strength of the balsa wood. Afterwards, the panel was post-cured at 80°C for 7 hours.

2.1.3 Measurement instrumentation

A Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system was used to monitor the global displacement field from side B of the panel, where a fine black speckle pattern was applied over white ground paint (**Figure 1b**). Moreover, five pairs of axial Strain Gauges (SG) were mounted back-to-back on both sides of the plate (**Figure 2c**). SG1, SG2, and SG5 were aligned with the load axis (x-direction) while SG3, SG4, and

SG6 were applied at 90° to it. SG5 and SG6 were installed at the center of the plate, while all others were symmetrically placed around it, on a virtual circle with a radius of 150 mm.

Figure 2. a. Sandwich plate thickness measurements at the edges, b. adhesive at edge, and c. strain gauge positions measured from the center of the sandwich plate.

2.1.4 Experimental determination of buckling resistance

The critical buckling load F_{cr} , i.e., the buckling resistance, was determined using two methods. The first method involves analyzing the experimentally recorded load versus in-plane displacement diagram of the plate. Although there is no drop in load, just a reduction in the stiffness of the plate as suggested by Zaal [12], the buckling load is identified at the ordinate of the intersection point between the tangents of the pre- and post-buckling gradients (**Figure 3a**). In the second method, as described by Schuette [13], the buckling load is defined as the level at which the compressive strain on the convex side of the buckle crest stops increasing and begins to decrease, a method known as strain reversal (**Figure 3b**).

Figure 3. Experimental buckling loads: a. tangent method, b. strain reversal method.

2.2 Theoretical analyses

2.2.1 Material properties

The raw material properties listed in **Table 1** were used to calculate the lamina properties of the sandwich skin using a micro-mechanical approach, as introduced in [8]. Based on the thickness measurements, the skins were estimated to have a fiber volume fraction of 40%. The laminate properties (**Table 2**) were then calculated using Classical Laminated Plate Theory (CLPT). The raw material properties of the infusion resin and the adhesive were mechanically tested at Fraunhofer IWES according to international test standards. The glass fiber properties were sourced from the literature [8]. The balsa wood properties were derived from an experimental database using a curve-fitting approach that linearly correlates the material properties with the corresponding wood density [9].

Table 1. Raw material properties.

Material	E_{11} (MPa)	E_{22} (MPa)	E_{33} (MPa)	ν_{12} (-)	ν_{13} (-)	ν_{23} (-)	G_{12} (MPa)	G_{13} (MPa)	G_{23} (MPa)
Inf. Resin	3150	3150	3150	0.35	0.35	0.35	1167	1167	1167
Adhesive	4772	4772	4772	0.30	0.30	0.30	1835	1835	1835
Balsa	223	199	3784	0.43	0.06	0.06	22	203	197
Glass fib.	81000	81000	81000	0.22	0.22	0.22	33197	33197	33197

Table 2. Laminate properties.

Material	E_{xx} (MPa)	E_{yy} (MPa)	E_{zz} (MPa)	ν_{xy} (-)	ν_{xz} (-)	ν_{yz} (-)	G_{xy} (MPa)	G_{xz} (MPa)	G_{yz} (MPa)
Glass-FRP [±45 ₂]	8807	8850	8830	0.62	0.18	0.18	9518	2523	2523

2.2.2 Analytical sandwich plate model

The critical buckling resistance was estimated for a simply supported plate considering an orthotropic model according to Wiedemann [10], as described in [3]. The materials used and the coordinate system are illustrated in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Sandwich plate model parameters; based on [3].

The critical buckling value k is defined as

$$k = \frac{p_{xcr} b^2}{\sqrt{B_x B_y} \pi^2} = \frac{1}{\Phi_x} + a_{wm}^2 \left(\frac{1}{\Phi_y} - \frac{H_1 + H_2 - 2(v + \hat{v})}{(H_1 H_2 - (v + \hat{v})^2) \Phi_x \Phi_y} \right) \quad (1)$$

where p_{xcr} is the critical buckling resistance and b the width of the sandwich plate. The help functions H_1 and H_2 are defined as

$$H_1 = \frac{\Phi_y \left(1 + \frac{\hat{v}}{a_{wm}^2}\right) + 1}{\Phi_x} \quad (2)$$

and

$$H_2 = \frac{\Phi_x(1 + \hat{v}a_{wm}^2) + a_{wm}^2}{\Phi_y} \quad (3)$$

The buckling ratio a_{wm} is given by

$$a_{wm} = \frac{a}{mb} \sqrt[4]{\frac{B_y}{B_x}} \quad (4)$$

where a is the length of the sandwich plate and m the number of buckling half waves. Poisson's ratio is determined as

$$v = \frac{D_{12}}{\sqrt{B_y B_x}} \quad (5)$$

and the drill stiffness number as

$$\hat{v} = \frac{D_{66}}{\sqrt{B_y B_x}} \quad (6)$$

where D_{ij} represents the terms of the bending stiffness matrix of the sandwich as described in [11], which can be determined using Classical Laminated Plate Theory (CLPT). B_x and B_y denote the matrix elements D_{11} and D_{22} , respectively. The core number in each plane direction is defined as

$$\Phi_y = \frac{\pi^2 B_y}{K_y b^2} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\Phi_x = \frac{\pi^2 \sqrt{B_y B_x}}{K_x b^2} \quad (8)$$

where the shear stiffness is defined as

$$K = \frac{G_c d^2}{h} \quad (9)$$

where G_c is the through-the-thickness core shear stiffness (G_{13} and G_{23} in **Table 1**) and d is defined as

$$d = h + \bar{t}_f \quad (10)$$

with \bar{t}_f as the arithmetic mean thickness of the two skins t_{ft} and t_{fb} . h denotes the thickness of the core.

2.2.3 Finite element model

A three-dimensional finite element model was developed in ANSYS to predict the bifurcation load, i.e., the buckling resistance, of the sandwich plate. The material properties used are detailed in **Table 1** and **Table 2**. Each skin layer of the model was represented by a single element in the thickness direction. The adhesive at the top and bottom of the test plate at the load introduction points was also modeled. In

total, 68,375 eight-node brick elements of type SOLID185 were utilized. At the virtual panel edges, the rotational degrees of freedom were left free, simulating the degrees of freedom provided by the test load frame. A compressive force was applied vertically at the top of the plate (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Finite element model of the plate: a. boundaries and mesh, b. zoom-in of corner.

3. Results and discussion

From the DIC displacement recordings, it is clear that the plate was deforming according to the first buckling eigenmode (**Figure 6a**). The negative displacement indicates that the monitored surface (side B) was deflecting out-of-plane towards the viewer. This observation is corroborated by the strain gauge measurements along the load axis. The diminishing recordings suggest that, although the plate was under compression, the developed dimple caused side B to bend out-of-plane, adding positive deformation to the overall negative displacement. This phenomenon explains the strain reversal that occurred at the buckling load, as defined in Chapter 2.1.4., before the final collapse (**Figure 6b**).

Based on the force-displacement diagram shown in **Figure 3a**, it is evident that the panel exhibits limited post-buckling performance in terms of displacement. After a slight drop in stiffness, the plate failed, as illustrated in **Figure 7**. Delaminations were observed at the lower right edge of the plate at side A, and cracks along the lower edge of side B, which ultimately led to the final failure.

Figure 6. Side B: a. out-of-plane displ., b. strain-gauges along load axis

Figure 7. Post-mortem specimen: a. Side A, b. Side B

The theoretical buckling load predictions are presented in Table 3, alongside the experimentally determined buckling loads.

Table 3. Summary of theoretical and experimental buckling loads

	Tangent of pre- & post buckling (Exp.)	Strain reversal (Exp.)	Analytical model	Linear bifurcation analysis (FE)
F_{cr} in kN	299	310	314	316

The theoretically determined buckling loads overestimate the experimentally determined buckling loads by 1.3% to 5.7%. The tangent method yields a more conservative buckling load than the strain reversal method. Both the analytical and numerical predictions are in good agreement with each other, differing by only 0.6%.

The lower experimental values could be a result of imperfections in the plate geometry, structure, and load introduction. The analytical and numerical models do not account for these imperfections, hence they predict higher buckling loads. However, it is noteworthy that in this proof-of-concept case, the discrepancy was relatively small.

4. Conclusions

A novel test load frame was introduced to enhance the experimental design validation of the critical buckling load of thick composite sandwich plates, as found in wind turbine blades. A proof-of-concept test was successfully conducted, confirming the expected performance and validating both analytical and numerical predictions. The compressed sandwich panel deformed in the anticipated first buckling eigenmode, as recorded by a DIC (Digital Image Correlation) system. Moreover, the theoretically determined buckling loads overestimated the experimentally determined buckling loads by 1.3% to 5.7%, while the analytical and numerical predictions were in good agreement with each other.

Future finite element analyses should consider geometric imperfections to further reduce the remaining discrepancy between the model and experiment.

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